

Socio Economic Impact of Health Insurance – A Study in Mumbai

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Abstract

The health insurance sector in India is only a few decades old. However, it has a deep-rooted history and the traces found in writings of Manu (Manusmithi), Yagnavalkya (Dharmashastra), and Kautilya (Arthashastra). It's mentioned how the pooling of resources helpful during calamities like floods, fire, and epidemics. Health insurance plays a pivotal role in shaping the socio-economic landscape of a nation, influencing individuals, families, and communities in various ways. Its impact is multifaceted, ranging from personal well-being to broader economic stability. This paper explores the socio-economic implications of health insurance, focusing on key aspects such as accessibility, financial protection, and overall societal welfare. The main aims of this paper is to highlight the positive impact that comprehensive health coverage can have on society

Keywords- Health Insurance, Financial Inclusion, Insurance Premium, Financial Protection

Introduction:

The health insurance concept was first suggested in the year 1694 by Hugh the Elder Chamberlen from Peter Chamberlen family. As a result, "Accident Assurance" began to be available in the 19th Century. However, in the middle to late 20th-century traditional disability insurance evolved into new health insurance programs. After that, with several amendments and innovations, health insurance came into existence. For the last 50 years, India has also achieved a lot in terms of health insurance. Left with no stone unturned, the health insurance sector gaining popularity in India. At present, health insurance is one of the emerging sectors in India. Different stakeholders of this ecosystem, such as private health insurance companies, IRDAI, and other entities, are thriving each day to come up with the best health insurance policy for every citizen. Indians become the most active and engaged customers when it comes to health insurance. After pandemic, buying cashless health insurance online is a new normal. This increasing attention and awareness are due to rising medical inflation, advancements in medical sciences, pandemic, and critical illnesses. Thus, the Indian Health insurance market has come up with lucrative growth avenues and opportunities for companies and customers.

Medical insurance, also known as health insurance, is a type of coverage that provides financial protection for individuals or groups against the costs associated with medical and healthcare services. It typically pays for a portion or the entirety of medical expenses, including doctor visits, hospital stays, prescription medications, surgeries, and preventive care. Medical insurance can be obtained through private insurance companies or government programs, and the specific coverage and costs vary depending on the policy and the insurer. It is designed to help

individuals manage and mitigate the financial burden of healthcare expenses.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To analyze the socio economic profile of the households
2. To identify the reasons for not having health insurance

Hypothesis of the Study:

H1- There is a significant relationship between educational qualification and having health insurance policy.

H0- There is no significant relationship between educational qualification and having health insurance policy.

Research Methodology:

The research methodology adopted for this paper has been illustrated here. The study adopts descriptive research design with sample survey approach. The present study makes use of both primary and secondary data to analyze the Socio Economic impact of Health insurance. The primary data was collected from sample households from the selected sample ward through simple random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire was used to collect all relevant information for the study. The questionnaire provides information about socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the households. Secondary data was collected from different publications, articles journals and survey reports of BMC. Sample size is limited to 130 as per the sample size calculator. To know the socio economic profile of the sample households, the study collected the variables like, age, gender, caste, marital status, occupation, religion, family size and type of family. The computer program, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 20) is used to analyze the data. The mean standard deviation, percentage and frequencies were first calculated to get

the initial reaction of the respondents to each item in the questionnaire. All items were analyzed using

descriptive statistics.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The socio economic profile of the households:

1.1 Age Wise Details of Respondents

Table 1.1 Age of Respondents

Age	No. of Respondents
21-30 years	29
31-40 years	42
41-50 years	35
51-60 years	22
Above 60 years	2
Grand Total	130

Source: Primary Data

Fig. 1.1 Age of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

The above table no.1.1 and graph no.1.1 shows age of the respondents. There were 29 respondents in the age group of 21-30 years, 42 were from 31-40 years, 35 were from 41-50 years, 22 were

from 51-60 years and 2 were above 60 years. Regarding the age of respondents, majority were below 40 years.

Table 1.2 Gender of Respondents

Gender	No. of Respondents
Female	58
Male	72
Grand Total	130

Source: Primary Data

Fig. 1.2 Gender of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

Gender Wise Information: The above table no. 1.2 and graph no.1.2 shows gender of the respondents.

There were 72 male respondents and 58 female respondents.

Table 1.3 Educational Qualifications of Respondents

Educational Qualification	No. of Respondents
Upto SSC	12
HSC	32
Graduation	48
Post Graduation	38
Grand Total	130

Source: Primary Data

Fig. 1.3 Educational Qualification of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

Educational Qualification Wise Details of Respondents:

The above table no.1.3 and graph no. 1.3 shows educational qualification of the respondents. There were 12 respondents studied up to SSC, 32 were

studied up to HSC, 48 were studied up to graduation and 38 were studied up to post-graduation. Regarding the educational Qualification of respondents, majority were graduation and above.

Table 1.4 Occupation of Respondents

Occupation	No. of Respondents
Salaried Employee	89
Self - Employed	18
Professional / Freelancers	7
Student	10
Retired	1
Other	5
Grand Total	130

Source: Primary Data

Fig. 1.4 Occupation of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

Occupation Wise Details of Respondents:

The above table no. 1.4 and graph no. 1.4 shows occupation of the respondents. 89 were salaried / employed, 18 respondents were self-employed, 7

were professional / freelancers, 10 were students 1 was retired and 5 were in other occupation. Regarding the occupation of respondents, majority were salaried employees.

Table 1.5 Monthly Income of Respondents

Monthly Income	No. of Respondents
Less than Rs. 20,000/-	32
Rs.20,001/- to Rs.40,000/-	42
Rs.40,001/- to Rs.60,000/-	26
Rs.60,001/- to Rs.80,000/-	16
Above Rs. 80,000/-	14
Grand Total	130

Source: Primary Data

Fig. 1.5 Monthly Income of Respondents

Source: Primary Data

Income Wise Details of Respondents:

The above table no. 1.5 and graph no. 1.5 shows monthly income of the respondents. 32 were having monthly income less than Rs.20,000/-, 42 were having Rs.20,001/- to Rs.40,000/-, 26 were having Rs.40,001/- to Rs.60,000/-, 16 were having Rs.60,001/- to Rs.80,000/- and 14 were having monthly income above Rs.80,000/-.

insurance of respondents. Non-insurance respondents conveyed the main reason for not taking insurance like higher premium, complex T&C and free treatment facility in BMC hospitals. And about 45% of them are presently take treatment from BMC hospitals. Rest of the 55% respondents prefers to take treatment from private and trust hospitals at their own expense. More than 90% of them have never taken health insurance in the past.

Reasons for not having health insurance: Table No. 1.6 shows the different reasons for not having health

Table 1.6 Reason for not having health insurance

Particulars	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Premium of health insurance is too much for me	7	18	18	4	1
Terms and Conditions health insurance are very rigid and ambiguous	7	20	17	3	1
I am ok with paying bills for private hospitals for treatment	4	9	15	12	8
I am happy with treatment in BMC hospitals since it is free	10	13	15	7	3
Health insurance is rarely used and premium goes waste	6	9	22	6	5

Source: Primary data

Fig. 1.6 Reason for not having health insurance

Source: Primary Data

The above graph no. 1.6 shows that most of the respondents were agree and neutral about premium of health insurance is too much for me. They were agree that terms and conditions health insurance are very rigid and ambiguous. They were neutral about I am ok with paying bills for private hospitals for treatment

and at the same time significant number of respondents were disagree with it. They were neutral followed by agree with I am happy with treatment in BMC hospitals since it is free. They were neutral about health insurance is rarely used and premium goes waste.

1.7 Chi-square Contingency Table Test for Independence

		I have Employee State Insurance (ESIC)	I have PradhanMantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PM-JAY), Ayushman Bharat Yojana or other Yojana	Yes, I have purchased	Yes, My company has provided me	No, I don't have any health insurance	Total
Upto SSC	Observed	0	1	3	7	1	12
	Expected	0.65	0.83	3.05	3.05	4.43	12
	% of chisq	3.50%	0.20%	0.00%	27.70%	14.30%	45.60%
HSC	Observed	1	0	10	7	14	32
	Expected	1.72	2.22	8.12	8.12	11.82	32
	% of chisq	1.60%	11.90%	2.30%	0.80%	2.20%	18.90%
Graduation	Observed	5	4	10	8	21	48
	Expected	2.58	3.32	12.18	12.18	17.72	48
	% of chisq	12.20%	0.70%	2.10%	7.70%	3.30%	26.00%
Post-Graduation	Observed	1	4	10	11	12	38
	Expected	2.05	2.63	9.65	9.65	14.03	38
	% of chisq	2.90%	3.80%	0.10%	1.00%	1.60%	9.40%
Total	Observed	7	9	33	33	48	130
	Expected	7	9	33	33	48	130
	% of chisq	20.20%	16.70%	4.50%	37.30%	21.30%	100.00%
		18.56	chi-square				
		12	df				
		0.0998	p-value				

The chi-square test was applied and the results show that the chi-square value is 18.56 and p value = 0.0998, which is more than 0.05 therefore H_0 is accepted which states that there is no relation between educational qualification and having health insurance policy i.e. educational qualification does not affect buying health insurance policy.

Findings:

Socio economic profile of the respondents

- The primary data shows that majority of respondents were come under the category of below 40 years of age.
- Gender wise information shows that there were 72 male respondents and 58 female respondents.
- Regarding the educational Qualification of respondents, majority were graduation and above.
- Occupation wise details of the of respondents shows that majority were salaried employees.
- Regarding the monthly income of respondents, majority were reported up to Rs. 40,000.

Reasons for not having Health Insurance

Non-insurance respondents conveyed the main reason for not taking insurance like higher premium, complex T&C and free treatment facility in BMC hospitals. And about 45% of them are presently take treatment from BMC hospitals. Rest of the 55% respondents prefers to take treatment from private and trust hospitals at their own expense. More than 90% of them have never taken health insurance in the past. The data shows that those who do not have health insurance, 21 respondents of them said they go to BMC hospitals for the treatment, 16 said they go to Private hospitals and 11 said they prefer to go to Trust hospitals for the treatment.

Majority of health insurance availed respondents preferred to take it for the entire family, i.e. Family Health Insurance. Friends and family have influenced most of the respondents to buy health insurance mainly to save medical cost. Most of the respondents are satisfied with the benefits and would like to continue/ renew the health insurance.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

In the long term, investing in health insurance programs is a strategic move for governments aiming to build a resilient and prosperous society. The financial protection offered by health insurance allows individuals to allocate their resources towards education, housing, and entrepreneurship, creating a foundation for socio-economic advancement. Moreover, it acts as a stabilizing force during unforeseen health crises, preventing families from falling into poverty due to medical expenses.

Health insurance is a fundamental pillar for socio-economic development. It not only protects individuals from the financial burden of healthcare but

also contributes to a healthier, more productive workforce and fosters social equity. Governments and societies that prioritize accessible and affordable health coverage are investing in the well-being and prosperity of their citizens, laying the groundwork for sustained development.

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